

Physical activity promotion to people with spinal cord injury by health professionals: A scoping study

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Abstract. Purpose: Health professionals are in an ideal position to promote physical activity and have been identified by people with spinal cord injury (SCI) as valued messengers of physical activity information. The purpose of this scoping study was to identify and map the literature related to physical activity promotion by health professionals to people with SCI. The specific aims were to 1) ascertain the extent, range and nature of the literature, 2) explore the key characteristics of the body of evidence for successful physical activity promotion and 3) identify the main barriers and facilitators of physical activity promotion by health professionals to people with SCI. **Methods:** A comprehensive search of key databases was undertaken. Following application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 18 studies were included for review. **Results:** Health professionals across studies predominantly included physiotherapists but also comprised occupational therapists, nurses, personal trainers and exercise/leisure therapists. Most studies delivered interventions by health professionals to increase physical activity in people with SCI in both in-patient and community settings. Interventions containing tailored exercise programs, behavioural components and on-going counselling support were considered essential for increasing physical activity motivation, self-efficacy and behaviour. Other studies sought to understand and/or improve physical activity promotion behaviour in health professionals. There were multiple barriers that constrained physical activity promotion including a lack of education and training. A need to improve and sustain physical activity knowledge was identified if physical activity promotion is to become a structured and integral component of practice. **Conclusion:** This study provides valuable information for the design of interventions to increase physical activity participation in people with SCI and improve physical activity promotion by health professionals.

Keywords Physical activity, promotion, spinal cord injury, health professionals

Introduction

Physical activity has been identified as a means to alleviate or prevent many of the secondary health and well-being complications following spinal cord injury (SCI). Yet people with SCI face multiple barriers to leading a physically active lifestyle (Williams et al. 2014). Health professionals are in an ideal position to promote physical activity and have been identified by people with SCI as valued and trusted messengers of physical activity information (Faulkner et al. 2010).

Therefore, it is important to understand the contexts in which effective physical activity promotion by health professionals may occur.

The purpose of this scoping study was to identify and map the literature related to physical activity promotion by health professionals to people with SCI. The specific aims were to 1) ascertain the extent, range and nature of the literature, 2) explore the key characteristics of the body of evidence for successful physical activity promotion and 3) identify the main barriers and facilitators of physical activity promotion by health professionals to people with SCI.

Methods

Search strategy

Scoping study methodology was drawn upon to guide the search and analysis of articles (Arksey & O'Malley 2005, Levac et al. 2010). Specific terms for physical activity (e.g., exercise, wellbeing, fitness, training etc.), promotion (e.g., intervention, advice, counsel etc.) and SCI (e.g., paraplegia, tetraplegia, spinal cord lesion etc.) were used to perform searches on key databases (CINAHL, Medline, PsychARTICES, PsychINFO, SPORTDiscus) to identify articles published since the year 2000 to July 2018.

Screening

Articles were first screened based on the relevance of the title to the purpose of the study. The abstracts of the remaining articles were then screened according to the following inclusion criteria: i) original article published in a peer-reviewed journal reporting empirical research, ii) articles that presented data related to physical activity interventions delivered by health professionals to people with SCI, interventions to improve physical activity knowledge of health professionals regarding SCI, or factors that influence physical activity promotion by health professionals to people with SCI, and iii) published in English.

Data extraction and synthesis

Data were extracted from the full text articles including article information, physical activity promotion strategies, barriers and facilitators to physical activity promotion by health professionals and future research and practical implications.

Results

A total of 2102 articles were identified. Following screening, 18 articles met the inclusion criteria. These articles were mostly from North America and Europe, with health professionals predominantly consisting of physiotherapists but also comprising others including healthcare professionals and exercise and leisure trainers and therapists.

Articles sought to examine a variety of contexts through a range of study designs. Many studies delivered interventions by health professionals to increase physical activity in people with SCI in both in-patient and community settings. The aim of these studies was to explore the experiences of people with SCI partaking in interventions delivered by health professionals and evaluate the efficacy of physical activity interventions. Interventions containing tailored exercise programs, behavioural components and on-going counselling support were considered essential for increasing physical activity motivation, self-efficacy and behaviour.

Other studies sought to understand and/or improve physical activity promotion behaviour in health professionals. These studies included examining health professionals' knowledge of physical activity for people with SCI and understanding their perceptions and experience of

physical activity promotion. Multiple barriers that constrained physical activity promotion were revealed, such as a lack of education and training. Evidence-based strategies and resources for health professionals were shown to increase physical activity promotion.

Conclusion and discussion

People with SCI value the inclusion of health professionals in interventions to increase physical activity. Health professionals should draw upon evidence-based strategies and resources to increase the efficacy of physical activity interventions. However, there is a need to improve and sustain physical activity knowledge if physical activity promotion is to become a structured and integral component of health professionals' practice.

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